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LINKAGES BETWEEN EXPENDITURE ON HEALTH AND EDUCATION IN INDIA: DYNAMIC ECONOMETRIC APPROACH THROUGH LAG MODELS

Ashok Bhukta¹ & Dr. Sudhakar Patra²

INTRODUCTION

Health is an input and necessary condition for education. It is the outcome of effective quality education and an important sector that must collaborate with education. The objective of universal primary education is directly related to the health of children. Health and education are mutually related to each other. While education leads to the development of people, health ensures the efficiency and sustainability of people. Health and education is an important and basic input required to improve the quality of human resources. The financial outlays by the centre and state governments were generally on the lower side. Mid-term appraisal of the 10th five-year plan by the planning commission admits that “social sector like education and health have in the past, not received the desired level of financial support both from the centre and the states due to financial constraints. Increased public spending on health and education and successful public-private partnership, for creating social infrastructure and successful delivery of services, is the need of the hour”. It further emphasizes that to bridge the divide between the haves and have-nots and to ensure economic progress of the latter, access to quality basic education and health care is imperative not only to reduce social and regional disparities but also to achieve balanced growth and development. While funding for health and education programmes in Budget 2018-19 appears to be the highest over the last three years. The estimated budgetary expenditure on health and education for 2018-19 is now Rs.1.38 lakh crore, a 13 per cent rise over the estimated expenditure of Rs.1.22 lakh Crore in 2017-18. The article has four sections. Section-I provides a review of literature and objectives. Time period of analysis and Sources of data, definitions of the variables and the statistical techniques and specification of the Lag Model used in the article are explained in Section-II, Section-III provides Analysis and results of the study, Section-IV presents finding, suggestions and conclusions.

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LITERATURE REVIEW

There is a plethora of literature on health expenditure but an attempt is made to review a few important literatures. **Rout, Himanshu (2010)** in his article analysed the gender bias (or unbiased) in the HHE based on primary data collected from four districts of Odisha, India, by adopting multi-stage random sampling method. To substantiate the gender bias (or unbiased) in health expenditure, multiple regression analysis is used and descriptive statistics are estimated. The result shows that there is a significant difference between the average male and female HHE in rural, urban and combined areas but not in tribal areas. To reduce the gender disparity in HHE long-term and sustained improvements in women's and men's health is required. This may be brought out through expansion of education and economic opportunities among men and women. **Bhadra K.K., Bhadra J (2012)** examined various factors affecting low public expenditure on health across states in India. The study revealed the level of public spending on health for the centre and states combined remains less than 1 % of the Gross Domestic Product. The paper disclosed the status of the states in meeting their committed liabilities which leaves very little room to spend on health. It also discussed the role and contribution of finance commission towards complete equalization across the states. **Rout. S.K. (2010)** studied to examine the pattern of and trends in public expenditure on health care in Odisha, with a special focus on expenditure on reproductive and child health services. The study covered a 12 year period from 1996-97 to 2007-08. **Rout. S.K. (2010)** highlighted why is education associated with good health? The theoretical explanation fall into three categories: 1. Work and economic condition, 2. Social psychological resources, and 3. Health lifestyle. According to the first explanation, well-educated people are less likely to be unemployed and more likely to full-time job, fulfilling work, high incomes, and low economic hardship. According to the second, the well-educated have social-psychological resources. According to the third, the well-educated have healthier lifestyle; compare to the poorly educated, the well-educated are more likely to exercise, to drink moderately, to receive preventive medical care, and less likely to smoke. **Kwabena Gyimah and Brepong (2010)** traced the effects of education on several development outcomes in Asian countries. Education had a positive and significant impact on development outcomes. Primary and secondary education was more important for some development outcomes but for outcomes like income growth rate, tertiary education was of greater significance. All levels of education had a positive impact on growth. Education brought about positive significant health benefits. Primary and secondary education had a stronger impact on preventive health programmes- immunization, HIV/AIDS prevalence and also reduction of IMR. With respect

to political outcomes like women's participation in parliament, secondary education had positive significant results.

Objective

- To study the nature and trend of total expenditure on Health and Education in India.
- To study the Linkages/Correlation between Expenditure on Health and Education in India.

Time Period of Analysis

The variables taken for analysis are the health care expenditure of India and the state government expenditure on education. The time period of health care expenditure taken for analysis is 2001-02 to 2017-18 and the data on state government expenditure on education are taken for the period from 2001-02 to 2017-18. The data on health care expenditure and expenditure on education are deflated to 2001-02 prices so that inflationary effect is removed from the data on both the variables.

Sources of Data

The data required for analysis have been taken from the various issues of economic survey, Government of India. The study is based on secondary data collected from Indiastat, Odisha stat, National Health Accounts, RBI Database, World Bank Database, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare.

Methodological Design of the Lag Model Used

A lag model is an active model in which the effect of a regressor X on Y follows over time. In the simple case of one descriptive variable and a linear relationship, I can write the model as Y_t be the value of education for the year t and X_t be the value of the state government expenditure in the year t. The relationship between Y_t and X_t can be studied through a simple Linear Regression model of the form

$$Y_t = \alpha + \beta_0 X_t + u_t$$

Where u_t is the error term, explanatory variable X_t , estimate α and β 's of may adopt two approaches: (1) ad hoc estimation and (2) a priori restriction on the β 's by assuming that the β 's follow some systematic pattern.

However, this model assumes implicitly that the current year expenditure on education and health influences the current year of education expenditure and it has no time lag. However, to identify the time lag, though the explanatory power of the independent variable, namely, the government expenditure on education and health, we should run regression models with varying time lag. Hence, if a time lag of one year is used, the above model becomes

$$Y_t = \alpha + \beta_0 X_t + \beta_1 X_{t-1} + \beta_2 X_{t-2} + u_t$$

and if a time lag of k ($k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$) years is used, the model becomes

$$Y_{t=} \alpha + \beta_0 X_t + \beta_1 X_{t-k} + u_t \quad k = 1, 2, 3...$$

A VAR model specifies that the conditional mean is a function of only a finite number of lags:

$$E (y_t / F_{t-1}) = E (y_t / y_{t-1}, \dots, y_{t-k})$$

A linear VAR specifies that the conditional mean is linear in the arguments:

$$E (y_t / y_{t-1}) = \alpha + \beta_1 y_{t-1} + \beta_2 y_{t-2} + \dots + \beta_k y_{t-k}$$

Based on the data collection, the value of k has been varied from 1 to 12. Since the data on education expenditure are taken for analysis from the year 2001-02 when k (lags) = 0, education expenditure is regressed on the government expenditure on education and health corresponding to each year. When k=1, the influence of the expenditure on education and health in the year t-1 on the education expenditure of the year t (2001-02) is studied through the model. Similarly, if k = 13, the influence of the government expenditure on health in the year t-14 is studied.

Conceptual Problems

Theoretical, the expenditure on health may have its impact on the education in the succeeding years and therefore the distributed lag model can study the influence of the expenditure on health in earlier years on current education. However, such a model has the same independent variable as different independent variable with a time lag of one or two. It leads to the problem of multicollinearity and the results of the regression show a very high value of coefficient of determination, with insignificant coefficients. As such distributed lag models do not serve the purpose here. In general, the data on the expenditure will have an increasing trend due to the rising trend of economic activities. As a consequence, the expenditure on health may be capable of explaining the variations in education by a higher degree. Therefore the value of the coefficient of determination will be higher. However to identify the goodness of fit more coefficient, the value of the F statistic, the correlation coefficient are also used in this analysis. In the case of time-series data, the OLS estimators are not efficient and they do not have minimum variance. The confidence interval, therefore, becomes unnecessarily wide and the test of significance becomes less powerful. Hence, the regression model should be checked for the presence of autocorrelation and model to explain the phenomenon. For all the lag models fitted, the Durbin-Watson statistic is also estimated to identify whether autocorrelation is present or not in the model.

HEALTH EXPENDITURE BUDGET FOR INDIA

In the Budget, the finance minister focused on the health sector and introduced a new national health insurance scheme it was declared “the world’s largest” to insure 100 million households for Rs 500,000 per family per year. To meet these ambitious targets, however,

there has only been a 2.7 per cent increase in allocations to the health sector, from Rs 53,198 crore in 2017-18 (revised estimates) to Rs 54,667 crore (Budget estimate). Spending on the health ministry has declined to 2.1 per cent of the total Union Budget from 2.4 per cent in 2017-18. Health expenditure should be 2.5 per cent of gross domestic product (GDP) by 2025, according to the National Health Policy.

Table 1

Health Expenditure in India from 2014-2019

Year	Ministry of Health & Family Welfare Budget (In Rs. Crore)	Total Central Budget (In Rs. Crore)	Share of total Central Budget (In per cent)
2014-15	33121.42	1794891.96	1.8
2015-16	30626.39	1777477.04	1.7
2016-17	37671.3	1978060.45	1.9
2017-18*	51550.85	2146734.78	2.4
2018-19**	52800	2442213.3	2.1

Source: Union Budgets; *Revised estimate, **Budget estimate

The table shows that a 2.1 per cent decline in the allocation towards the national health mission, India's largest programme for primary health infrastructure; A 0.23 percentage point decline over 2017-18 in the Union Budget's share of funding to the Human Resource Development (HRD) ministry, making it the lowest since 2014-15. A 1.7 % cut in allocation for the health expenditure on Budget from 2017-18's revised estimates. To fund the increased spending announced for 2018-19, a health and education cess that taxpayers pay would rise to 4 per cent from 3 per cent. "This will enable us to collect an estimated additional amount of 11,000 Crores," as he presented the Budget in 2018.

Source: Computed by own author

Above the figure, 2.1% decline in the allocation for the National Health Mission a national health programme that funds infrastructure for primary healthcare from Rs 31,292 crore in 2017-18 (revised estimates) to Rs 30,634 crore (budget estimate). On a positive, the budget for the National Nutrition Mission a programme that seeks to reduce stunting, under

healthcare expenditure in rose over three times, from Rs 950 crore in 2017-18 (revised estimates) to Rs 3,000 crore in 2018-19 (budget estimate). The poly. Trend line rose increasing order from 2014-2019. The result shows on $y=42420x-88129x$ and $R^2=0.99$ over trend period in the total central budget. This restores the government’s commitment to improving nutrition status among Indian children after the programme’s budget was cut in the revised estimate for 2017-18. From an allocation of Rs 1,500 crore, the revised estimate came down 36.6 per cent to Rs 950 crore for that year. India has 48.2 million stunted short for their age children, more than any other country in 2018.

Table 2
Health Expenditure in India from 2001-2014

Year	Total H.E (% of GDP)	Public H.E (% of GDP)	Public H.E (% of Govt. Expenditure)	Public H.E (% of Total Health Expenditure)
2001	4.5	1.08	4.25	23.97
2002	4.4	1.03	3.82	23.31
2003	4.3	0.98	3.6	22.92
2004	4.22	1.02	4.04	24.23
2005	4.28	1.13	4.51	26.49
2006	4.25	1.11	4.4	26.15
2007	4.23	1.1	4.43	26.02
2008	4.34	1.16	4.34	26.79
2009	4.38	1.22	4.37	27.9
2010	4.28	1.16	4.29	27.13
2011	4.33	1.18	4.42	27.14
2012	4.39	1.18	4.49	26.97
2013	4.53	1.29	4.66	28.41
2014	4.69	1.41	5.05	30.04

Sources: - World Bank DataBase

The public expenditure on health and education may be influencing the status of health directly and more prominently compare with other macro-economic variables. Table-2 shows the data on the percentage of health and education expenditure in the total public sector outlay since 2001. The table shows that the percentage of health expenditure was ranging from 4 to 5 per cent of the total outlay.

Source: Computed by own author

The percentage of health expenditure in the total public sector outlay was just less than 1.08 per cent until 2001. It was on an average 4 per cent in the late 2005's but it was around 5% in the middle of 2008. Percentage of both the public % of govt. and total health expenditure was, on an average, 4.34 percentages for the same period.

Table 3

Results on multivariate time series of VAR lag model test on Health Expenditure in India from to 2001-2014

Lag	LL	LR	df	p	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBIC
0	37.80				1.5e-10	-11.26	-11.26	-11.40
1	.	.	16	.	0*	.	.	.
2	785.28	.	16	.	.	-253.76	-257.09	-254.59
3	785.95	1.34	16	1.00	.	-253.98	-257.32	-254.82
4	.	.	16
5	805.53	.	16	.	.	-260.51*	-263.84*	-261.34*
6	773.78	-63.49	16	.	.	-249.93	-253.26	-250.76
7	775.06	2.56	16	1.00	.	-250.35	-253.69	-251.19
8	787.08	24.02	16	0.09	.	-254.36	-257.69	-255.19

Regression Analyses

Source	SS	Df	MS	Number of obs= 14, F (3, 10) = 424.78,			
Model	0.22	3	0.75	Prob> F = 0.00, R-squared = 0.99,			
Residual	0.00	10	0.00	Adj R-squared = 0.99,			
Total	0.22	13	0.75	Root MSE = 0.01			
Total of GDP	Coef.	Std.Err.	T	P > t	95% Conf.	interval	
Public of gdp	3.47	0.11	30.26	0.00	3.21	3.72	
Public of govt. expenditure	0.00	0.03	0.04	0.96	-0.06	0.06	
Public of total health expenditure	-0.15	0.00	-23.20	0.00	-0.15	-0.14	
_cons	4.40	0.05	78.18	0.00	4.27	4.52	

Source: Computed by STATA

The estimated R^2 reveals that the level of health expenditure explains $R^2 = 0.99$, $t=78.18$, $F=424.78$, the model reveals that the independent variable influences the level of health expenditure is statically significant as the estimated 't' (0.04) value is greater than the table value. The whole model is statistically significant as the estimated 'f' value is greater than the table value.

EDUCATION IN BUDGET

The government has defined learning outcomes and conducted a national survey of more than 2 million children to assess the on-ground status of education in the country. This will help in devising a district-wise strategy for improving quality of education, Allocating Rs 85,010 crore to the HRD ministry. In absolute terms, this Budget of Rs 85,010 crore breaks a declining trend in allocation to the HRD ministry under the government and is a Rs 5,324 crore or 6.7 per cent rise from 2017-18, when Rs 79,685 crore was allocated. 8uuu

Table 4

Education Expenditure in India from 2014-2019

Year	Human Resource Development Ministry Budget (In Rs. Crore)	Total Central Budget (In Rs. Crore)
2014-15	1,10,351.10	1,794,891.96
2015-16	96,649.76	1,777,477.04
2016-17	92,666.65	1,978,060.45
2017-18	79,685.95	2,146,734.78
2018-19	85,010.29	2,442,213.30

Source: Union Budgets; All figures are Budget estimates

However, as a share of the total Union Budget, the HRD ministry's allocation has dropped 0.23 percentage points to 3.48 per cent in 2018-19 the lowest since 2014-15 from 3.71 per cent in 2017-18. In five years to 2018-19, that is a drop of 2.7 percentage points to 3.48 per cent from 6.15 per cent in 2014-15.

Source: Computed by own author

The figure shows that the Improvement in quality of teachers can improve the quality of education in the country, introducing integrated bachelors of education programme. Poly. Trend line increasing to 2018-19. The result shows $y = 166390x + 2E+06$, $R^2 = 0.9069$. In 2016, a million teaching posts 900,000 in elementary schools and 100,000 posts in secondary schools were vacant in 2016.

Table 5
Government of India Expenditure on Education from to 2001-2013

Year	Total Edu. Exp (% of GDP)	Total (% of Govt. Expenditure)	Tertiary Education (% of Govt. expenditure on education)	Secondary education (% of Govt. expenditure on education)	Primary Education (% of Govt. expenditure on education)
2001	3.9	11.51	20.23	39.54	35.09
2002	3.5	11.52	20.58	38.52	36.07
2003	3.66	12.41	20.09	41.67	36.08
2004	3.40	11.2	20.01	41.62	36.38
2005	3.23	11.21	19.55	42.89	35.59
2006	3.19	11.69	20.28	42.54	35.38
2007	2.2	11.59	23.58	42.62	35.29
2008	2.2	11.23	33.56	35.53	26.98
2009	3.31	11.19	36.45	34.92	26.68

2010	3.42	11.83	36.08	36.99	25.21
2011	3.84	13.56	34.68	36.96	26.55
2012	3.87	13.99	32.17	38.73	27.21
2013	3.84	14.05	28.53	41.35	28.4

Source- World Bank Data

The public expenditure on education may be influencing the status of education directly and more prominently compare with other macro-economic variables. Table-2 shows the data on the percentage of total education expenditure in the 3.9 outlay since 2001 and reduces in 3.84 forms 2013. The table shows that the percentage of education expenditure was ranging from 11.51 to 13.99 per cent of the total outlay.

Source: Computed by own author

The figure shows that the Improvement in quality of teachers can improve the quality of education in the country, introducing integrated bachelors of education programme. Poly. Trend line increasing to $y = 0.1845x + 10.784$, $R^2 = 0.4436$ in total education expenditure in India from 2001-19.

Table 6

Result of multivariate time series of VAR lag model test in Government of India Expenditure on Education from to 2001-2013

Lag	LL	LR	df	p	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBIC
0	-12.91	.	16	.	0.01	6.76	5.92	6.45
1	.	.	16
2	627.86	.	16	.	.	-243.14	-247.39	-244.71
3	631.49	7.25	16

Regression Analyses

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs= 13, F (4, 8) = 3.54, Prob> F = 0.06, R-squared = 0.63, Adj R-squared = 0.45, Root MSE = 0.18			
Model	0.47	4	0.12				
Residual	0.26	8	0.03				
Total	0.73	12	0.06				
Total of GDP	Coef.	Std.Err.	T	P > t	95% Conf.	interval	
Total of govt.	0.22	0.07	3.19	0.01	0.62	0.38	

expenditure						
Tertiary edu. of expenditure	-0.02	-0.01	-0.43	0.68	-0.12	0.08
Secondary edu. of expenditure	-0.07	-0.06	-1.78	0.11	-0.15	0.02
Primary edu. of expenditure	0.01	0.01	0.17	0.87	-0.14	0.16
_cons	3.61	3.95	0.91	0.39	-5.52	12.73

Source: Computed by STATA

The table of Result in multivariate time series of VAR lag model test in Government of India Expenditure on Education from to 2001-2013 in total of lags in 4 and showing in different results in the table.

ANALYSIS OF DYNAMIC ECONOMETRIC APPROACH THROUGH LAG MODELS

The estimator of the parameter of lag models have been fitted through the OLS method. The estimated value of the regression coefficient (a), constant term (b), standard error of the regression coefficient (SE), t value (T), level of significance, R², Adjusted R², Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation (R), F statistic (F) and Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic are given below table. An econometric analysis of the relationship between is estimated as real expenditure on health and education sectors in India.

Table 7

Results of the Lagged Regression Models

Lagged Regression Models for Health Expenditure from 2001-2013								
Time Lag Model	Change Statistics							
(k)	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	Durbin-Watson		
1	.99 ^a	.99	.01	.99	424.78	2.56		
2	.71 ^a	.50	.09	.50	12.21			
3	.99 ^b	.99	.01	.49	688.90	2.56		

Correlation Coefficients						
Time Lag Model	Unstandardized Coefficients			Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	
1 (Constant)	3.40	.27		12.38	.00	
Public (% Of GDP)	.83	.24	.71	3.49	.00	
2 to 3 (Constant)	4.40	.05		84.23	.00	
Public (% Of GDP)	3.47	.10	2.95	33.00	.00	
Public (% Of Total Health Expenditure)	-.15	.00	-2.35	-26.25	.00	

Lagged Regression Models for Health Expenditure from 2014-2019								
Time Lag Model	Change Statistics							
	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	Durbin-Watson		
4	.99 ^a	.99	33261.09	.99	136.97	2.09		
5	.93 ^a	.88	112036.59	.8	21.32			
6	.99 ^b	.99	33261.09	.11	32.04	2.09		

Correlation Coefficients

Time Lag Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
4 (Constant)	1002648.65	227622.08			4.40	.02
Ministry of Health & Family Welfare Budget (In Rs. Crore)	24.91	5.39	.94		4.62	.02
5 to 6 (Constant)	1789614.68	154586.37			11.58	.01
Ministry of Health & Family Welfare Budget (In Rs. Crore)	44.27	3.78	1.66		11.72	.01
Share of total Central Budget (In percent)	-799797.59	141301.00	-.80		-5.66	.03

Table 8**Lagged Regression Models for Education Expenditure from 2001-2013**

Time Lag Model	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics			Durbin-Watson
				R Square Change	F Change		
7	.80 ^a	.64	.46	.18	.64	3.54	2.15
8	.70 ^a	.49	.45	.18	.49	10.72	1.19
9	.00 ^b	.00	.00	.25	-.64	3.54	
10	.72 ^c	.52	.42	.19	-.12	3.03	
11	.70 ^d	.49	.45	.18	-.02	.46	1.19

Correlation Coefficients

Time Lag Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
7 to 11 (Constant)	3.61	3.96			.91	.39
Total (% of Govt. Expenditure)	.22	.07	.98		3.19	.01
Tertiary Education (% of Govt. expenditure on education)	-.02	.04	-.53		-.43	.68
Secondary education (% of Govt. expenditure on education)	-.07	.04	-.75		-1.78	.11
Primary Education (% of Govt. expenditure on education)	.01	.07	.21		.17	.87

Lagged Regression Models for Education Expenditure from 2014-2019

Time Lag Model	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics			Durbin-Watson
				R Square Change	F Change		
12	.92 ^a	.84	.79	127816.74	.84	15.68	
13	.99 ^b	.99	.98	41977.32	.15	25.81	2.57

Correlation Coefficients

Time Lag Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
12 (Constant)	3077694.78	271166.98			11.35	.00
Share of total Central Budget (In percent)	-223746.65	56494.84	-.92		-3.96	.03
13 (Constant)	1701873.91	285058.03			5.97	.03
Share of total Central Budget (In percent)	-518490.03	60906.38	-2.12		-8.51	.01

Human Resource Development Ministry Budget (In Rs. Crore)	29.70	5.85	1.27	5.08	.04
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Source: Computed to SPSS by Own Author

The overall impact of health expenditure and various levels of education has been substantial over the period of time. Data availability was a major consideration in the choice of time period and countries. The results may vary depending on the selection of country and the time period under consideration. Better results may emerge if a longer time period is considered.

1. Correlation coefficient

The correlation coefficient is around of highest 4.80 health expenditure and 3.61 education expenditure in the beginning and as the time lag increases, correlation coefficient start exceeding 1.07 and it becomes higher and higher. It reaches 1.07 when the time lag is 19 years. As the time lag exceeds 13, again the correlation coefficient starts registering a general expenditure on health is the highest when the time lag is 13.

2. Regression coefficient

The regression coefficient are relatively smaller in the initial stages and they increase when the time lag increase. Health expenditure in India, Results on multivariate time series of VAR lag model test on Health Expenditure in India from to 2001-2014 in Number of obs= 14, F (3, 10) = 424.78, Prob> F = 0.00, R-squared = 0.99, Adj R-squared = 0.99, Root MSE = 0.01. Result of multivariate time series of VAR lag model test in Government of India Expenditure on Education from to 2001-2013 and Education expenditure in India, Result of multivariate time series of VAR lag model test in Government of India Expenditure on Education from to 2001-2013, Number of obs= 13, F (4, 8) = 3.54, Prob> F = 0.06, R-squared = 0.63, Adj R-squared = 0.45, Root MSE = 0.18 This is due to the fact that the values if the education expenditure in recent years is relatively higher compared to the values of the expenditure on health in the earlier period. The regression coefficient increase from and varies around one hundred when k ranges between time lags 1 to 13. When k exceeds 13, regression coefficient starts increasing from 143 and reaches 243 when k = 13.

3. Standard error

Standard error is an indicator of the variance of the parameter. An estimator is regarded as the best estimator if it has minimum variance. Therefore, the model in which the standard error is less will be the better model. The standard error is reducing as a k increases and it becomes the least when k = 13. The value of the highest standard error is 3.96 and 5.39 when k = 13 and as a k exceeds 13, standard error increase stage by stage and it touches the highest value 285058.03 when K = 13. Thus the variance and the standard error of the parameters is relatively less in the range $10 = k \leq 13$.

4. ‘T’ value and the level of significance

All the regression coefficients are statistically significant and in all cases, the level of significance is less than one per cent. The value of level significance of 't' statistic ranges between the lags 1 to 5. It increases and touches the highest value 78.18 and 0.91 in constant when $k = 13$. It starts declining when k exceeds 13.

5. Coefficient of determination

The value of the adjusted R^2 reveals the fact that the government expenditure on health is capable of explaining more than 60 per cent of variations in expenditure in education whatever the time lag be. However, the value of adjusted R^2 shows an increasing trend when k increases. The highest value of adjusted R^2 is 0.919 when $k = 1$. This clearly indicates the fact that the explanatory power of the government expenditure on health reaches the highest level of 92 per cent when the time lag is 14 years. After this stage, the value of adjusted R^2 starts declining. Therefore, the inference is that government expenditure on health has its impact on the national income at the highest level after a time lag of 14 years for the Odisha during the period under investigation.

6. 'F' value

The F statistic also reveals this fact. It touches the highest value of health and education expenditure (136.97 and 10.72) when the time lag is 13. Thus the estimated parameters have the highest degree of significance when $k = 13$. In the beginning, it is comparatively less and it increases as k increases. However, F statistic starts declining after k exceeds 13. The ANOVA through regression also support the fact that the parameters become highly significant when the time lag is 13.

7. Durbin Watson statistic

The Durbin Watson statistic for one explanatory variable and 13 observations at 1% level of significance is $d_L = 2.19$ and $d_U = 2.56$. Hence if the calculated value of d lies in between 2.56 and 2.57, the test becomes inconclusive and $d < d_L$, the error terms are positively autocorrelated. In case if $d > d_U$, we need not reject the Null Hypothesis that the error term is independently distributed. The calculated value of d is very low in the beginning and it indicates the presence of positive autocorrelation till $k = 8$. The error terms are positively correlated even in the range $6 < k < 13$. However, the error terms are not positively correlated when $k = 13$. In this case, the calculated value of d is 2.19 and it is greater than the $d_U = 2.56$. Since $d < 4 - d_U$ (i.e., $2.19 < 2.56$), the error terms are not negatively correlated also when time lag is 13. Therefore, the lag model is free from autocorrelation when the time lag is 13. In this case, the OLS estimators become unbiased and the best parameters and hence can be used for prediction.

FINDINGS AND SUGGESTION

Health is an input and necessary conditions for education. It is an outcome of effectively quality education and an important sector that must collaborate with education. The objective of 'universal primary education' is directly related to the health of children. Health and education are mutually related to each other. The improvement in one leads to the improvement in another. While education leads to the development of people, health ensures the efficiency and sustainability of people.

CONCLUSION

The access to health and education is a prior condition of inclusive development. In spite of the rapid economic growth, there are the challenges of universal access to quality education and health facilities for the downtrodden still existing in our society. Actually, inclusive development can happen only when opportunities are created for all persons without negative discrimination. Increase in the access to health and education is a significant area where government can advance some new steps to ensure inclusive development to all people. Empirical evidence from the correlation analysis shows that tertiary education may help in increasing the per capita GDP growth rates and secondary education may help in inclusive growth. The regression results shows the possibility of health expenditure and also enrolment in different levels of education having an impact on health and education expenditure. The study concludes that the level of health and education expenditure influences the level of total expenditure positively. The government may enhance the percentage of expenditure on health and education in the total outlay.

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